

MUSICGALAXY – AN ADAPTIVE USER-INTERFACE FOR EXPLORATORY MUSIC RETRIEVAL

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ABSTRACT

Sometimes users of a music retrieval system are not able to explicitly state what they are looking for. They rather want to browse a collection in order to get an overview and to discover interesting content. A common approach for browsing a collection relies on a similarity-preserving projection of objects (tracks, albums or artists) onto the (typically two-dimensional) display space. Inevitably, this implicates the use of dimension reduction techniques that cannot always preserve neighborhood and thus introduce distortions of the similarity space. This paper describes ongoing work on MusicGalaxy – an interactive user-interface based on an adaptive non-linear multi-focus zoom lens that alleviates the impact of projection distortions. Furthermore, the interface allows manipulation of the neighborhoods as well as the projection by weighting different facets of music similarity. This way the visualization can be adapted to the user's way of exploring the collection. Apart from the current interface prototype, findings from early evaluations are presented.

1. INTRODUCTION

There is a lot of ongoing research in the field of music retrieval aiming to improve retrieval results for queries posed as text, sung, hummed or by example as well as to automatically tag and categorize songs. All these efforts facilitate scenarios where the user is able to somehow formulate a query – either by describing the song or by giving examples. But what if the user cannot pose a query because the search goal is not clearly defined? E.g., he might look for background music for a photo slide show but does not know where to start. All he knows is that he can tell if it is the right music the moment he hears it. In such a case, exploratory retrieval systems can help by providing an overview of the collection and letting the user decide which regions to explore further.

When it comes to get an overview of a music collection, neighborhood-preserving projection techniques have become increasingly popular. Beforehand, the objects to be projected – depending on the approach, this may be

artists, albums, tracks or any combination thereof – are analyzed to extract a set of descriptive features. (Alternatively, feature information may also be annotated manually or collected from external sources such as the EchoNest API¹.) Based on these features, the objects can be compared – or more specifically: appropriate distance- or similarity measures can be defined. The general objective of the projection can then be paraphrased as follows: Arrange the objects in two or three dimensions (on the display) in such a way that neighboring objects are very similar and the similarity decreases with increasing object distance (on the display). Popular dimensionality reduction techniques for such a neighborhood-preserving projection are self-organizing maps (SOM) [1], principal component analysis (PCA) [2] and multidimensional scaling techniques (MDS) [3]. As the feature space of the objects to be projected usually has far more dimensions than the display space, the projection inevitably causes some loss of information – irrespective of which dimensionality reduction techniques is applied. Consequently, this leads to a distorted display of the neighborhoods such that some objects will appear closer than they actually are, and on the other hand some objects that are distant in the projection may in fact be neighbors in feature space.

Another problem that arises when working with similarity-based neighborhoods is that music similarity is highly subjective and may depend on a person's background. Consequently, there is more than one way to look at a music collection – or more specifically to compare two tracks based on their features: A musician, for instance, might especially look after structures, harmonics or instrumentation (possibly paying – conscious- or unconsciously – special attention to his own instrument). Non-musicians will perhaps focus more on overall timbre or general mood. Others, in turn, may have a high interest in the lyrics as long as they are able to understand the particular language. A music retrieval system should be able to incorporate this subjectiveness in order to better comply with the individual needs of its users and consequently gain a higher acceptance. To this end, the system presented in this paper allows the user to modify the underlying distance measure by adapting weights for different aspects of similarity. Further, the described user-interface exploits the above mentioned distorted neighborhood relations during user-interaction. The approach is based on a multi-focus fish-eye lens that allows a user to enlarge and explore a region

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¹ <http://developer.echonest.com/>

of interest while at the same time adaptively distorting the remaining collection to reveal distant regions with similar tracks.

A broad overview of related work and a discussion of computational complexity aspects has been given in [4]. This paper focuses primarily on the user-interface and the interaction. To this end, the fundamental preprocessing steps are reviewed in Section 2. Section 3 covers important aspects of the visualization with Section 3.2 focusing on the SpringLens distortion technique in particular as the basis for the user-interaction. The user-interaction is described in Section 4. Specifically, Section 4.2 provides insight into how the neighborhood distortions caused by the projection are addressed. The evaluation process of the user-interface is described by Section 5. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. DATA PREPROCESSING

This section sketches all necessary preprocessing steps that can be done offline, i.e. before the actual interaction with the user. For a detailed description, we refer to [4].

2.1 Feature Extraction

The prototype system described here uses collections of music tracks. As a prerequisite, it is assumed that the tracks need to be represented by some descriptive features that can, e.g., be extracted, manually annotated or obtained from external sources. In the current implementation, content-based features are extracted utilizing the capabilities of the frameworks CoMIRVA [5] and JAudio [6]. Specifically, Gaussian Mixture Models of the Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCCs) according to [7] and [8] and "fluctuation patterns" describing how strong and fast beats are played within specific frequency bands [9] are computed with CoMIRVA. JAudio is used to extract a global audio descriptor "MARSYAS07" as described in [10]. Further, lyrics for all songs were obtained through the web service of LyricWiki², filtered for stop words, stemmed and described by document vectors with TFxIDF term weights [11]. Additional features that are currently only used for the visualization are ID3 tags (artist, album, title, track number and year) extracted from the audio files, track play counts obtained from a last.fm profile, and album covers gathered through web search.

2.2 Facet Definition

Based on the features associated with the tracks, *facets* are defined that refer to different aspects of music (dis-) similarity:

Definition Given a set of features F , let S be the space determined by the feature values for a set of objects O . A *facet distance metric* d (or short: *facet*) is a distance metric defined on a subspace $S' \subseteq S$ of the feature space and satisfying the following conditions for any $x, y, z \in O$:

- $d(x, y) \geq 0$ and $d(x, y) = 0$ if and only if $x = y$

² <http://lyricwiki.org>

facet name	feature	distance metric
timbre	GMM of MFCCs	euclidean distance
rhythm	fluctuation patterns	euclidean distance
dynamics	MARSYAS07	euclidean distance
lyrics	TFxIDF vectors	cosine distance

Table 1. Facets defined for the current implementation.

- $d(x, y) = d(y, x)$ (symmetry)
- $d(x, z) \leq d(x, y) + d(y, z)$ (triangle inequality)

For instance a facet "timbre" could be defined on the MFCC-based feature described in [8] whereas a facet "text" could compare the combined information from the features "title" and "lyrics".³

In order to be able to aggregate values from several facet distance metrics, the following normalization is applied for all distance values v of a facet d :

$$v' = \min\left\{1, \frac{v}{\mu + \sigma}\right\}$$

where μ is the mean and σ the standard deviation of all distance values with respect to d . This truncates very high distance values and results in a value range of $[0, 1]$. For the aggregation, basically any function could be used. In the current prototype the following parametrized aggregation functions are predefined:

- $d = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^l w_i d_i^2}$ (weighted euclidean distance)
- $d = \sum_{i=1}^l w_i d_i^2$ (squared weighted eucl. distance)
- $d = \sum_{i=1}^l w_i d_i$ (weighted sum)
- $d = \max_{i=1..l} \{w_i d_i\}$ (maximum)
- $d = \min_{i=1..l} \{w_i d_i\}$ (minimum)

The aggregation functions allow to control the importance of the facet distances d_1, \dots, d_l through their associated weights w_1, \dots, w_l . Default settings for the facet weights and the aggregation function are defined by an expert (who also defined the facets themselves) and can later be adapted by the user during interaction with the interface. Table 1 lists the facets used in the current implementation.

2.3 Indexing

A small sample of tracks is drawn from the collection with the objective to approximate the covariance matrix of the whole collection. These tracks are referred to as *landmarks*. Only for these tracks, the projection will be computed later. The remaining tracks will be placed according to their distances to the landmarks. This reduces the computational complexity of the projection method and facilitates near real-time updates in case of parameter changes.

³ It is important to stress the difference to common faceted browsing and search approaches that rely on a faceted classification of objects to support users in exploration by filtering available information. Here, no such filtering by value is applied. Instead, we employ the concept of facet distances to express different aspects of (dis-)similarity that can be used for filtering.

Figure 1. Facet distance cuboid data structure holding the distance values for N tracks, m landmarks and l facets.

To further speed up the projection, the distances to all landmarks are precomputed and stored in a 3-dimensional data structure called "facet distance cuboid" (Figure 1) that holds for each song the distance values to all landmarks for all facets. (As it is not clear at indexing time how the facet distance values are to be aggregated, the values need to be stored separately.) Note that the space requirement effectively scales linearly with the number of tracks as the number of landmarks and facets can be considered small or even constant in comparison so that the data structure should fit into RAM even for large collections.

Further, a neighbor index needs to be constructed to facilitate fast lookup of neighbors during the interaction. Currently, nearest neighbors are precomputed for each track and updated each time the facet aggregation parameters change. This is not appropriate for large collections and efficient indexing techniques need to be investigated in future work. Possible candidates are space partition trees [12] or approaches based on locality sensitive hashing [13] that may even be kernelized [14] to allow for more complex distance metrics. However, as our current research focus lies on the user-interface, this is only a secondary problem.

3. VISUALIZATION

3.1 Projection Technique

Before the collection can be projected, the facet distances need to be aggregated. The facet distance cuboid (c.f. Section 2.3) already holds the precomputed facet distance values. I.e., for each (track, landmark)-pair, a list of values referring to the respective facets can be looked up. The parametrized aggregation function that computes a single value from such a list can be fully controlled by the user.

In the projection step, each track is mapped from the high-dimensional feature space to a 2-D-coordinate that will later be used to infer its position when displayed on the screen. Naturally, this projection should be neighborhood-preserving such that tracks close to each other in feature space are also close in the projection. We apply a landmark- or pivot-based multidimensional scaling approach (LMDS) for the projection as described in detail in [15, 16]. This is a computationally efficient approximation to classical MDS that is feasible for application on large data sets as it scales linearly with the size of the data set. The general idea of

this approach is as follows: Given the sample of landmark objects selected during preprocessing by some heuristic, an embedding into low-dimensional space is computed for these objects using classical MDS. Each remaining data object can then be located within this space according to its distances to the landmarks.

3.2 Distortion Technique

Once the 2-D-positions of all tracks are computed, the collection could already be displayed. However, an intermediate distortion step is introduced that serves as the basis for the interaction techniques described later.

The distortion technique is based on an approach originally developed to model complex nonlinear distortions of images called "SpringLens" [17]. A SpringLens consists of a mesh of mass particles and interconnecting springs that form a rectangular grid with fixed resolution. Through the springs, forces are exerted between neighboring particles affecting their motion. By changing the rest-length of selected springs, the mesh can be distorted. The deformation is calculated by a simple iterative physical simulation over time. This way, the SpringLens functions as a very flexible lens.

In the context of this work, we apply SpringLens to simulate a complex superimposition of multiple fish-eye lenses. We chose a moderate resolution with a maximum of 50 cells in each dimension for the overlay mesh which yields sufficient distortion accuracy while real-time capability is maintained. The distorted position of the projection points is obtained by barycentric coordinate transformation with respect to the particle points of the mesh. Additionally, z-values are derived from the rest-lengths that are used in the visualization.

3.3 Visualization Metaphor

The music collection is visualized as a galaxy. Each track is displayed as a star or as its album cover. The brightness and (to some extent) the hue of stars depends on a predefined importance measure. In the current implementation, this is simply the play count (imported from last.fm). However, it would as well be possible to use (user) ratings or sophisticated popularity measures. The size and the z-order (i.e. the order of objects along the z-axis) of the objects depends on their distortion z-values. Optionally, the SpringLens mesh overlay can be displayed. The visualization then resembles the space-time distortions well known from gravitational and relativistic physics.

3.4 Filtering

In order to reduce the amount of information displayed at a time, the user can choose between different filters that decide whether a track is displayed collapsed or expanded – i.e. as a star or album cover respectively. The resulting display using these filter modes are shown in Figure 2. Apart from collapsing or expanding all tracks, it is possible to expand only those tracks in magnified regions (i.e. with a z-level above a predefined threshold) or to apply a *sparser filter*.

A sparser filter selects only a subset of the collection to be expanded that is both, sparse (well distributed) and representative. Representative tracks are those with a high importance – a feature (currently the play count) that also influences a star’s brightness and hue.

The first sparser version used a Delaunay triangulation constructed incrementally top-down starting with one big triangle. If the size of a triangle exceeds this threshold, the most important track within this triangle is chosen for display and added as a point for the triangulation. This process continues recursively until no triangle that exceeds a minimum size threshold contains anymore tracks that could be added.

The currently used sparser employs a different strategy: It divides the display into a grid of quadratic cells. The size of the cells depends on the screen resolution and the minimal display size of the album covers. Further, it maintains a list of the tracks ranked by importance that is precomputed and only needs to be updated when the importance values change. On an update, the sparser runs through its ranked list. For each track it determines the respective grid cell. If the cell and the surrounding cells are empty, the track is expanded and its cell blocked. (Checking surrounding cells avoids image overlap. The necessary radius for the surrounding can be derived from the cell and cover sizes.) This sparser approach produces more appealing results in terms of the spatial distribution of displayed covers.

Originally, the set of expanded tracks was updated after any position changes caused by the distortion overlay. However, this was considered irritating during early user tests and the sparser strategy was changed to update only if the projection or the displayed region changes.

4. INTERACTION

The user-interface as shown in Figure 3 allows several ways of interacting with the visualization⁴: Users can explore the collection through common panning & zooming (Section 4.1). Alternatively, they can use the adaptive multi-focus technique introduced with this prototype (Section 4.2). Further, they can change the facet aggregation function parameters and this way adapt the view on the collection according to their preferences (Section 4.3). Hovering over a track displays its title and a double-click start the playback that can be controlled by the player widget at the bottom of the interface. Apart from this, several display parameters can be changed such as the filtering mode (Section 3.4), the size of the displayed album covers or the visibility of the SpringLens overlay mesh.

4.1 Panning & Zooming

Panning shifts the displayed region whereas zooming decreases or increases it. These are very common interaction techniques that can e.g. be found in programs for geo-data visualization or image editing. Using the keyboard, the user can pan with the cursor keys and zoom in and out with + and – respectively. Alternatively, the mouse can

be used: Clicking and holding the left button while moving the mouse pans the display. The mouse wheel controls the zoom level. If not the whole region can be displayed, an overview window indicating the current section is shown in the top left corner, otherwise it is hidden. Clicking into the overview window centers the display around the respective point. Further, the user can drag the section indicator around which also results in panning.

4.2 Focusing

This interaction techniques allows to visualize – and to some extent alleviate – the neighborhood distortions introduced by the dimensionality reduction during the projection. The approach is based on a multi-focus fish-eye lens that is implemented using the SpringLens distortion technique (Section 3.2). It consists of a user-controlled *primary focus* and a neighborhood-driven *secondary focus*.

The primary focus is a common fish-eye lens. By moving this lens around (holding the right mouse button), the user can zoom into regions of interest. In contrast to the basic linear zooming function described in Section 4.1, this results in a nonlinear distortion of the projection. As a result, the region of interest is enlarged making more space to display details. At the same time, less interesting regions are compacted. This way, the user can inspect closely the region of interest without losing the overview as his field of view is not narrowed (as opposed to the linear zoom). The visual effect produced by the primary zoom resembles a 2-dimensional version of the popular “cover flow” effect.

The secondary focus consist of multiple such fish-eye lenses. These lenses are smaller and cannot be controlled by the user but are automatically adapted depending on the primary focus. When the primary focus changes, the neighbor index (Section 2.3) is queried with the track closest to the center of focus. If nearest neighbors are returned that are not in the primary focus, secondary lenses are added at the respective positions. As a result, the overall distortion of the projection brings the distant nearest neighbors back closer to the focused region of interest. Figure 4 shows the primary and secondary focus with visible SpringLens mesh overlay.

As it can become very tiring to hold the right mouse button while moving the focus around, the latest prototype introduces a focus lock mode (toggled with the return key). In this mode, the user clicks once to start a focus change and a second time to freeze the focus. Further, in the previous prototype, the secondary focus was always updated instantly when the primary focus changed. In the current version, this behavior can be disabled resulting only in an update of the secondary focus once the primary focus does not change anymore.

4.3 Adapting the Aggregation Functions

Two facet control panels allow to adapt two aggregated distance metrics by choosing a function type (in a dropdown menu) and adjusting weights for the individual facets (through sliders). The first aggregated distance metric is applied to derive the track-landmark distances from the facet distance cuboid (c.f. Section 2.3). These distances

⁴ A demo-video is available at <http://www.dke-research.de/aucoma>

Figure 4. SpringLens distortion with only primary focus (top) and additional secondary focus (bottom).

are then used to compute the projection of the collection. The second aggregated distance metric is applied to identify the nearest neighbors of a track and thus indirectly controls the secondary focus.

Changing the aggregation parameters results in a near real-time update of the display so that the impact of the change becomes immediately visible: In case of the parameters for the nearest neighbor search, some secondary focus region may disappear while somewhere else a new one appears with tracks now considered more similar. Here, the transitions are visualized smoothly due to the underlying physical simulation of the SpringLens grid. In contrast to this, a change of the projection similarity parameters has a more drastic impact on the visualization possibly resulting in a complete re-arrangement of all tracks. This is because the LMDS projection technique produces solutions that are unique only up to translation, rotation, and reflection and thus, even a small parameter change may, e.g., flip the visualization. As this may confuse users, one direction of future research is to investigate how the position of the landmarks can be constrained during the projection to produce more gradual changes.

The two aggregated distance metrics are linked by default as it is most natural to use the same metric for projection and neighbor retrieval. However, unlinking them and using e.g. orthogonal distance metrics can lead to interesting effects: For instance, one may choose to compute the

collection based solely on acoustic facets and find nearest neighbors for the secondary focus through lyrics similarity. Such a setting would help to uncover tracks with a similar topic that (most likely) sound very different.

5. EVALUATION

We follow a user-driven design approach [18] by iteratively alternating between development and evaluation phases. This paper describes the state after two significant revisions in the third development phase. The initial prototype (before the first evaluation) is described in [4] – focusing primarily on computational complexity and covering a performance evaluation of the projection and distortion methods. After some further refinements (including for instance the new sparser filter), this first prototype was presented at the CeBIT 2010 fair⁵ in early March 2010. During the fair, feedback was collected from a total of 112 visitors aged between 16 and 63 years. The general reception was very positive. The projection-based visualization was generally welcomed as an alternative to common list views. However, some remarked that additional semantics of the two display axis would greatly improve orientation. Young visitors particularly liked the interactivity of the visualization whereas older ones tended to have problems with this. They stated that the reason lay in the amount of information displayed which could still be overwhelming. To address the problem, they proposed to expand only tracks in focus, increase the size of objects in focus (compared to the others) and hide the mesh overlay as the focus would be already visualized by the expanded and enlarged objects. All of these proposals have been integrated into the second prototype that is very briefly described in [19].

The second prototype was tested thoroughly by three testers. During these tests, the eye movements of the users were recorded with an Tobii T60 eye-tracker. Using the adaptive SpringLens focus, the mouse generally followed the gaze that scans the border of the focus in order to decide on the direction to explore further. This resulted in a much smoother eye trajectory than the one observed during usage of panning and zooming where the gaze frequently switched between the overview window and the objects of interest – as not to lose orientation. This indicates that the proposed approach is less tiring for the eyes. However, the testers criticized the controls used to change the focus – especially having to hold the right mouse button all the time. This led to the introduction of the focus lock mode and several minor interface improvements not explicitly covered here.

The third prototype which is described in this paper will be tested in a larger eye-tracking study that aims to prove that the interface indeed helps during exploration.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This paper described an interactive user-interface that addresses a common problem of visualization approaches that

⁵ The CeBIT is a German trade fair specialized on IT – c.f. <http://www.cebit.de>

are based on neighborhood-preserving projections: Mapping music collections from high-dimensional feature space onto two dimensions, projection errors become inevitable. Therefore, some objects will appear closer than they actually are and on the other side, some objects that are distant in the projection may in fact be neighbors in the feature space. The described user-interface for exploring music collections exploits the distorted neighborhood relations during user-interaction: A multi-focus fish-eye lens is used to zoom into regions of interest. While the user can control the primary focus, the secondary focus is automatically adapted. It consists of multiple smaller fish-eye lenses that focus on regions that contain tracks that are similar to those in primary focus but have been projected elsewhere. This way, the projection errors can to some extent be compensated. Further, by choosing weights for different facets of similarity, the user can manipulate the projection and the neighborhood relations visualized by the lens.

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Figure 2. Available filter modes: collapse all (top left), focus (top right), sparse (bottom left), expand all (bottom right). The SpringLens mesh overlay is visible.

Figure 3. Screenshot of MusicGalaxy prototype with visible overview window (top left), player (bottom) and SpringLens mesh overlay (blue). In this example, a strong album effect can be observed as for the track in primary focus, four tracks of the same album are nearest neighbors in secondary focus.